

Knowledge Extraction and Ontology Modeling in the SALLY Chatbot

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Abstract. Reception and social integration of Third Country Nationals (TCNs) remains a pressing challenge in contemporary societies shaped by migration. The SALLY project supports the integration of migrants in Greece through a multilingual conversational agent designed to assist users in accessing information related to legal, healthcare, employment, and social services. This paper presents preliminary work on a knowledge extraction framework that captures key elements from natural language conversations—such as topics, entities, and relationships—using Large Language Models (LLMs). These are structured as RDF Knowledge Graphs guided by an ontology that reflects the dynamics of user-agent interaction. By translating informal dialogue into semantically meaningful representations, the system offers a foundation for better understanding user needs and behavior, while enhancing the transparency and responsiveness of the SALLY conversational agent.

Keywords: Knowledge Graphs · Large Language Models · Knowledge Extraction · Migrant Integration · Chatbot

1 Introduction

Migrant integration remains a significant challenge in many regions, including Greece, where Third Country Nationals (TCNs) often struggle to access relevant information about legal procedures, employment opportunities, healthcare services, and social support. Language barriers and fragmented resources frequently compound these difficulties, making reliable guidance hard to find. Recent progress in computational linguistics and artificial intelligence—especially through the use of Large Language Models (LLMs)—promises new ways to address these problems by enabling more adaptive, and multilingual tools.

In this context, SALLY develops a conversational agent designed to assist TCNs living in Greece. It integrates two core approaches: statistical, LLM-based methods for dialogue processing and semantic knowledge modeling through knowledge graphs. By operating in both Greek and English, the agent aims to facilitate communication and information dissemination among diverse user groups. A technical overview of the SALLY chatbot can be found in [2].

A key aspect of improving SALLY’s functionality is understanding how users interact with the system and identifying relevant patterns within these interactions. To address this, we have developed a knowledge extraction pipeline that processes user utterances and stores essential metadata, such as sentiment, entities, relations, and DBpedia links, using RDF. Our pipeline combines established libraries like spaCy [3] and DBpedia Spotlight [4] with custom solutions that utilize LLMs. The extracted information is then merged into a broader knowledge graph that records all of SALLY’s user-agent conversations, guided by an OWL ontology that formally defines the structure of these interactions.

This approach contributes to the broader challenge of making sense of humanistic data, specifically, natural language conversations that reflect users’ goals, concerns, and adaptation strategies in real-world social contexts. The ontology-based framework enables automated reasoning over this data, offering insights into migrant behavior, information-seeking patterns, and linguistic variation. By merging statistical methods with semantically structured knowledge, SALLY shows how linked data and the semantic web can be used to create more context-aware, transparent, and socially responsive conversational systems.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses related work, Section 3 presents the design of the knowledge extraction system, including the structure of the SALLY knowledge graph and the ontology used to represent conversations. Section 4 provides examples of extracted knowledge from conversations. Finally, Section 5 concludes with a summary of our contributions and suggestions for future research avenues.

2 Related work

Research on automating knowledge extraction has expanded in various directions, encompassing both rule-based techniques and machine learning approaches [5]. An early notable example is the work by Alani et al. [6], who proposed an ontology-guided framework that extracts structured information from unstructured web documents. Their method addresses the challenge of incomplete annotations by applying ontology-based rules, thus enhancing the depth and accuracy of the extracted content. Through the Artequakt project, it integrates a knowledge extraction tool with a domain ontology to automatically collect, structure, and maintain knowledge in a machine-readable format. A lexicon-based term expansion further enriches ontology terminology for more effective extraction. In the field of Digital Humanities (DH), specifically, recent advancements in deep neural networks have enabled automated tasks such as entity extraction and language detection. However, the application of neural networks in DH faces challenges like the availability of training data and domain adaptation. A recent study [7] provides a decision model for DH experts on when to apply deep learning techniques, highlighting the potential benefits of these approaches for DH research. Recently, [8] combined Open Knowledge Extraction (OKE) and NLP to build a Knowledge Graph from international private law texts. By applying legal ontology design patterns (event, time, role, agent, etc.), it captures key legal concepts and entities. Using experts’ critical questions, a question-answering tool

helps retrieve relevant legal information tied to specific topics, concepts, and normative references. Moreover, Resume2Skill-SE [9] is an end-to-end architecture that automates skill-based talent matching in large organizations. It combines unsupervised skills extraction using state-of-the-art text embeddings with a bipartite graph ranking module, reducing labeling costs, minimizing extraction errors, and providing interpretability by displaying shared skills between resume profiles. Finally, the ACME chatbot [10] was developed to assist asylum-seeking migrants in Europe, helping users identify the highest level of protection they can apply for, thus reducing the burden on territorial commissions and courts.

3 Description of the System

3.1 Description of the ontology

To support the SALLY knowledge graph, an OWL ontology was developed to formally specify how the graph should be structured. This ontology, therefore, serves as the framework for generating the SALLY knowledge graph, ensuring that all elements adhere to the definitions it provides. In our ontology, all sessions between SALLY and its users are included, and each session comprises the user utterances that form the conversation. Each utterance is associated with its text, topic, dialogue act, sentiment, language, and fluency, as well as any entities, private entities, and relations identified in the message. While the text, topic, sentiment, dialogue act, language, and fluency are stored as string values, the remaining elements demand more detailed modeling: entities include an entity name, its type, and a link to the corresponding DBpedia entry; private entities require both the entity type (for example, “country”) and the entity itself; and relations must specify their type, as well as the subject and object involved. Utterances are connected to each other in a sequential list-like fashion.

Below we list the classes included in our ontology, which was created using Protégé¹. The superclass for all of these classes is `owl:Thing`, and none of the classes contain any subclasses.

- **Session**: a conversation between some user and the chatbot. A resulting knowledge graph based on this ontology would be disconnected since no Session nodes are connected to each other by some edge.
- **Message**: an utterance (user utterances only).
- **Entity**: people, places, events, etc.
- **Private Entity**: entities that are sensitive in nature.
- **Relation**: triples of the form (subject, relation type, object). They connect entities.

3.2 Description of the knowledge extraction mechanism

The system begins with a conversation chatlog that contains only user utterances, processing these utterances one by one until all have been handled. Each

¹ <https://protege.stanford.edu>

Table 1. The data stored in the graph for each user utterance, along with a description.

Data	Description
Text	A short description of what the text is about.
Topic	The topic of the utterance.
Dialogue act	The aim of the user.
Sentiment	Description of the sentiment expressed by the user.
Language	The language the utterance is in.
Fluency	The fluency level of the utterance.
Entities	Entities found in the text, such as people and countries.
Private Entities	Entities that are private or sensitive information, such as names and nationalities.
Relations	Relations between the entities. These can be nationalities, familial relationships, and more. Relations are represented by triples (subject, type of relation, object).

utterance is initially translated into English using Google Translator from the Deep Translator package. Next, the system extracts the data types described in Table 1, excluding the textual content that is already available. A combination of existing tools, such as spaCy, and custom prompts to a large language model is employed for this task. Specifically, Llama 3.1 8B is utilized, chosen for its robust performance given its relatively small size. Table 1 outlines the metadata stored for each user’s utterance in a conversation, detailing the types of information that the system aims to extract.

Additionally, a separate knowledge graph is generated for each conversation, which is then merged with the overarching SALLY knowledge graph. The extracted elements are added to the conversation-specific graph immediately after identification. For demonstration purposes, `:session` refers to the session of the conversation (an instance of the class `Session`), and `:utterance` denotes a single user utterance (an instance of the class `Message`). In practice, both the session and each utterance receive unique names.

For simpler data types—*Topic*, *Dialogue Act*, *Sentiment*, *Language*, and *Fluency*—we store their values as strings via data properties. For more complex types—*Entity*, *Private Entity*, and *Relation*—we create individuals of these classes and link them to the relevant utterance using object properties. Below, we describe how each data type is extracted and stored:

- **Topic:** We rely on the LLM to extract the topic from a user utterance with a prompt such as:

Prompt for Topic Extraction

Your task is to recognize and classify the topic of the user’s query.

Once identified, we add `(:utterance, :topic, topic)` to the knowledge graph.

- **Dialogue Act:** To identify the dialogue act, we again use the LLM:

Prompt for Dialogue Act

```
Determine the dialogue act of the given user input/
question.
```

We then add (:utterance, :dialogueAct, dialogueAct) to the graph.

- **Sentiment:** The LLM is prompted to analyze sentiment:

Prompt for Sentiment Extraction

```
Your task is to act as a sentiment analysis system.
You have to understand and extract the sentiment from a
given text.
Be as precise as you can. Only return the sentiment you
found.
```

We record the sentiment with (:utterance, :sentiment, sentiment).

- **Language:** The Langdetect package identifies the language, which is stored with (:utterance, :language, language).
- **Fluency:** Fluency is determined by prompting the LLM:

Prompt for Fluency Evaluation

```
Your task is to find the fluency level of the given text
on a scale of 1 to 3,
where 1 represents low fluency and 3 represents high
fluency.
```

We add (:utterance, :fluency, fluency) to the graph.

- **Entities:** We run spaCy’s en_core_web_sm model for named entity recognition, extracting the entity text and its general category (e.g., PERSON). When possible, a DBpedia link is added using the DBpedia Spotlight API. We add:

Triples for Entity Extraction

```
(:rec_entity, a, :Entity)
(:utterance, :entity, :rec_entity)
(:rec_entity, :entityType, category_label)
(:rec_entity, :entityLink, DBpedia_link)
```

- **Private Entities:** Any entities referring to people or places are classified as private entities and stored similarly:

Triples for Private Entity Extraction

```
(:rec_priv_entity, a, :Private_Entity)
(:utterance, :privateEntity, :rec_priv_entity)
(:rec_priv_entity, :privateEntityType, category_label)
```

- **Relations:** A relation is a triple (subject, type of relation, object). We prompt the LLM to return JSON containing the predicate, subject, and object:

Prompt for Relation Extraction

```
You are an assistant who only generates JSON output in the
form described below.
Your task is to extract relations between these entities
from the given text: {user_text}.
...
```


Fig. 1. Visualization of a part of a conversation graph using Neo4j Bloom².

We then add:

```

Triples for Relation Extraction
(:rec_relation, a, :Relation)
(:utterance, :relation, :rec_relation)
(:rec_relation, :relationType, relation_type)
(:rec_relation, :relationSubject, subject)
(:rec_relation, :relationObject, object)

```

4 Results

In this section, we present the knowledge graphs obtained from three test conversations between users and the chatbot. Each conversation was processed by our knowledge extraction tool, which generated metadata-enriched graphs for further analysis. Figure 1 illustrates one of these conversations, where the session node (beige) contains three user messages (yellow). For the first user message—“Hi, I am Ahmed. I used to work as a civil engineer in Syria. I came to Greece with my wife and our two kids. I want to find a job here, any job.”—the system identified several entities (magenta) and automatically linked them to DBpedia. It also extracted various relations (blue), including (Ahmed, workedIn, Syria) and (Ahmed, locatedIn, Greece), and found corresponding private entities (not shown).

Figure 2 shows the combined knowledge graph for all three test conversations, incorporating the graph presented in Figure 1 as well as several additional utterance nodes. Notably, the system identifies the entity **Greece** in both the

² <https://neo4j.com/product/bloom/>

Fig. 2. Visualization of a part of the graph of all conversations using Bloom.

second conversation and the conversation depicted in Figure 1, thereby illustrating how the same entity may appear in multiple contexts. The end of each conversation is indicated by the `rdfl:nil` node (gray), which indicates that no further messages follow in that session. In addition, the system detects another domain-specific entity, **the Greek Council**, in the fourth message of the second conversation, showing how new references are captured and integrated into the knowledge graph.

5 Discussion & Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a knowledge extraction system designed to capture structured information from user–chatbot interactions within the SALLY project. Our approach combines existing solutions and custom LLM-based techniques to identify relevant data and export them to a knowledge graph. We discussed the ontology that underpins the extracted knowledge, specifying how the resulting graph should be constructed, and we described the data needed to model a conversation. Additionally, we outlined the pipeline responsible for extracting metadata from user utterances, populating the knowledge graph, and merging it with the overarching SALLY knowledge graph. Examples of test conversations illustrated the system’s capability to extract sentiment, entities, and relations.

By capturing linguistic and semantic patterns from real conversations, the system not only enhances the performance of SALLY as a multilingual support tool, but also provides a structured view into how users communicate needs, ask questions, and engage with digital assistance in complex social contexts. This opens the door to broader insights about user behavior and communication in situations where language, culture, and access to information intersect, highlighting the potential of such systems to support both technical and human-centered research.

Despite these advances, several challenges persist. The accuracy of knowledge extraction is tightly coupled to the reliability of the underlying tools, and user utterances containing ambiguous or domain-specific language can lead to inconsistencies. At present, there is also no efficient way to analyze the SALLY knowledge graph at scale, limiting our ability to draw broader insights regarding user interactions. Future work will focus on refining extraction techniques and developing a specialized chatbot for SALLY administrators, trained on the data in the SALLY knowledge graph, to more effectively study conversation patterns and improve the overall user experience.

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